

ORGANOMETALLIC COMPOUNDS OF THE ALLYL RADICAL. PART III ALLYL DERIVATIVES OF ARSENIC

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Triallyl arsine has been isolated by the action of allyl magnesium bromide on arsenic trihalides. Allyl cacodyl also seems to be a product of the reaction. Triallyl arsine and allyl bromide react in acetonitrile solution to form tetra-allyl arsonium bromide. Tetra-allyl arsonium bromide mercuribromide, and tetra-allyl arsonium picrate have been prepared. The quaternary base is also described.

A few organic compounds of arsenic containing the allyl radical are known. On heating mercuric arsenide with allyl iodide in a sealed tube, Partheil and Amort (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 596; *Arch. Pharm.*, 1899, 237, 127) obtained tetra-allyl arsonium iodide mercuri-iodide. Mannheim (*Annalen*, 1908, 341, 223) repeated these experiments and found that the products were double salts of tetra-allyl arsonium iodide and mercuric iodide. A few mixed arsonium compounds containing this radical (Burrows and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 484; Dehn and Wilcox, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 810; Winmill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 722), and phenyl methyl allyl arsine (Winmill, *loc. cit.*) and dimethyl allyl arsine (Dehn and Wilcox, *loc. cit.*) are also known. Allyl arsonic acid, $C_3H_5.ASO : (OH)_2$ and its sodium salt have also been prepared (Hofmann, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1921, 4, 1065; Quick and Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 810).

Triallyl arsine has now been prepared by the action of allyl magnesium bromide on arsenic trichloride in absolute ether medium.

The action of arsenic chloride on allyl magnesium bromide does not seem to be fully represented by the above simple equation. The yield of triallyl arsine is only about 40% of the theoretical. There is an appreciable amount of residue after distilling off the triallyl arsine. This residue fumes in air and in thin layers it burns readily forming fumes of arsenious oxide. It also explodes with oxygen and it has an intensely penetrating odour and is probably allyl cacodyl formed as a by-product.

From the residue obtained after distilling off the triallyl arsine, tetra-allyl arsonium bromide and picrate have been prepared, which more or less points to the fact that the residue is allyl cacodyl.

The action of arsenic tribromide on allyl magnesium bromide gives a lower yield than with arsenic chloride.

Richardson and Soper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 875) have found that additive reactions of trialkyl amines and alkyl iodides take place very smoothly giving good yields of the tetra-alkyl derivatives in a polar solvent of high cohesion like acetonitrile. Tetra-allyl arsonium bromide has been prepared from triallyl arsine and allyl bromide using acetonitrile as the solvent. Its mercuribromide derivative and tetra-allyl arsonium picrate have also been prepared. By the action of moist silver oxide on the bromide, a strongly alkaline syrupy

liquid is obtained which is confirmed to be the hydroxide by the preparation of tetra-allyl arsonium picorate from it.

Thus a study of the symmetrical allyls of the three metals, mercury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 589), tin (*ibid.*, 1945, 22, 135) and arsenic show that these compounds possess properties similar to other metal-alkyls and that the radical $CH_2 : CH.CH_2$ behaves in organometallic combination more or less similarly to the other alkyl radicals.

The metal-allyls undergo all the reactions characteristic of other metal-alkyls. It is interesting to note that both mercury diallyl and tin tetra-allyl part with one allyl radical with halogens, like bromine, in exchange for a halogen atom.

but do not form derivatives with one or more allyl radicals saturated by bromine, as for example, $CH_2Br.CHBr.CH_2HgC_2H_5$ or $(CH_2Br.CHBrCH_2)_2Hg$.

Halogen hydracids also affect these metal allyls in exactly the same way as they react with other metal alkyls. The action with the reactive hydrogen gives an indication of the comparative reactivity of organometallic compounds. Mercury diallyl is easily decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid (about 4%). Tin tetra-allyl is not acted upon by dilute hydrochloric acid except on heating, while concentrated acid decomposes it easily in the cold, whereas moderately concentrated hydrochloric acid decomposes arsenic triallyl only on boiling. The order of reactivity is in agreement with what one would expect. Relative reactivities depend upon the strength of the carbon-metal bond in the organometallic molecule and this latter can be correlated with the metallic nature of the central atom. With enhanced metallicity the bond would become weaker (*cf.* Gilman and Yale, *Chem. Rev.*, 1942, 30, 181).

It is surprising to note that mercury diallyl is not stable as was expected. The ethereal solution of the substance is fairly stable. Possibly the substance exists as a co-ordination complex in solution, as the Grignard reagents do, thus completing an octet round the central atom.

Tin tetra-allyl seems to be comparatively stable. This is to be expected as the central atom has a complete octet round it and quite probably it will behave as a perfectly non-polar liquid on account of the symmetrical structure of the compound.

Ammonia and phosphine do not combine with oxygen or chlorine directly to form compounds like $NH_3 \rightarrow O$ or $NH_3 \rightarrow Cl_2$ but substituted amines and phosphines form such compounds. The tendency of the unshared electron pairs in these compounds to be engaged in donor activity is enhanced by substitution. In saturated systems this activity is of course restricted to the hetero atom, but in an unsaturated system it may be transmitted through an intervening chain on account of the polarisability of the double bonds. Arsenic triallyl

shows a great tendency to unite with oxygen of the air. It combines with oxygen of the air quite readily, most probably forming the triallyl arsine oxide $(C_3H_5)_3As \rightarrow O$. The compound could not be prepared by exposing triallyl arsine to air as the product was contaminated with other oxidation products and gave a sticky mass. Other trialkyl arsines also behave similarly when exposed to air (Cahours, *Annalen*, 1864, 112, 230; Landolt, *Annalen*, 1854, 89, 329). Triallyl arsine also readily combines with allyl bromide to give the tetra-covalent ion $[(C_3H_5)_4As]^+$. The bromide is completely ionised in solution.

The alkalinity of the alkyl substituted bases like $(CH_3)_3NOH$ or $(CH_3)_3POH$ is greater than that of ammonia or phosphine. Tetra-ethyl arsonium hydroxide is quite a strong base precipitating hydroxides of heavy metals and liberating ammonia from ammonium salts (Landolt, *loc. cit.*). Tetra-allyl arsonium hydroxide is found to be alkaline to litmus and it precipitates hydroxides of copper and silver from the respective salts, but it does not liberate ammonia from ammonium salts. The basic nature of this quaternary base is less than that of the other tetra-alkyl arsonium hydroxides. This might be explained on the basis of the possibility of resonance between an arsenic atom and an unsaturated radical, just as the introduction of a phenyl group weakens the basic nature of ammonia.

EXPERIMENTAL

The arsenic chloride was prepared by the usual method of passing dry chlorine over heated arsenic and the arsenic bromide by the action of bromine on arsenic; these were purified by two distillations, and sucked up into weighed tubes with capillary necks and sealed. The allyl magnesium bromide was prepared as described by the author (previous part).

To the Grignard reagent from allyl bromide (28 g.) in absolute ether (250 c.c.) cooled to -15° with ice and salt, arsenic chloride (7 g.) dissolved in dry ether (50 c.c.) in the funnel f_2 (*vide* Part II) was added drop by drop with vigorous stirring. After all the arsenic chloride solution had been added, the mixture was allowed to warm up gradually to room temperature. A solid gradually appeared. It was found when concentrated solutions were used, too much solid separated all of a sudden and the stirrer got stuck up. The flask F and contents were left at room temperature for about 15 minutes. They were then cooled in ice and salt, and ice-cold ammonium chloride solution was added little by little with stirring. Cold dilute hydrochloric acid (about 3%) was added until the contents of the flask separated into two layers and the solid deposited on hydrolysis had dissolved. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether and the extracts dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide or sometimes hydrogen overnight.

The ethereal layer was siphoned into a two-necked flask under pressure of carbon dioxide. To one of the necks was fitted an one-holed cork carrying a delivery tube leading to a condenser and to the other a two-holed cork through one of which passed an inlet tube for carbon dioxide, and through the other, a weighed capsule with a drawn out neck. The ether was distilled off in a carbon dioxide atmosphere and the pale yellow coloured residual liquid was sucked up into the capsule, sealed, and preserved for use.

Since the liquid showed signs of decomposition in ordinary vacuum distillation, and was found to absorb oxygen from the atmosphere, it was distilled *in vacuo* twice in one

FIG. 1

operation in a special all-glass apparatus (see Fig. 1) which is an adaptation of a molecular still (Morton, "Laboratory Technique in Organic Chemistry", International Chemical Series, p. 120). The liquid in B_1 , with enough glass wool to prevent bumping was distilled from the water-bath at 50° at a pressure of 2 mm., the air in the apparatus being originally displaced by dry nitrogen. The condensate collecting at the internal joint C, was tilted down into B_2 and re-distilled. The liquid distilled at 41° and collected in R in which weighed capsules (only one shown in the figure) containing deep file marks were kept inverted before drawing off and sealing the open end E. On admitting dry nitrogen into the evacuated apparatus, the capsules got filled up with the liquid. The receiver R was cut open along a file mark below E and the capsules were taken out, carefully sealed immediately and used for analysis.

A capsule containing a weighed amount of the liquid was broken in concentrated hydrochloric acid in a long tube, and the tube was sealed and heated at 100° for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and at 150° for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The arsenic chloride solution so obtained was diluted, and the arsenic precipitated as arsenic sulphide and the precipitate dried at 105° to constant weight. For the combustion of the substance the last few centimeters of the usual cupric oxide filling of the combustion tube was replaced by lead peroxide which at the temperature of the furnace formed red lead, and retained the arsenic as lead arsenate (Falkov and Raiziss, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 998). The capsule containing the substance which had a deep file mark, was placed in a combustion boat and just before the boat was pushed in, a crack was started on the file mark by a red hot glass point. (Found: C, 54.67, 54.33; H, 7.59, 7.73; As, 37.72, 38.02. $\text{As}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ requires C, 54.51; H, 7.63; As, 37.84 per cent).

Triallyl arsine is a colourless, mobile liquid with a slightly penetrating odour. It is soluble in all the common organic solvents. It absorbs oxygen from the air with slight evolution of heat forming probably the oxide. On exposing the substance to air it becomes cloudy and gradually turns into a brown sticky mass. But the substance can be preserved in sealed ampoules in an atmosphere of an inert gas like nitrogen or carbon dioxide. It decolourises bromine and iodine in organic solvents. With strong mineral acids, the arsenic

is converted into the inorganic form with evolution of propylene, which was identified as the dibromide, b.p. 142°.

Tetra-allyl Arsonium Bromide.—To triallyl arsine (2 g.) dissolved in dry acetonitrile (10-15 c.c.) was added allyl bromide (2.4 g.) in acetonitrile (10-15 c.c.). The tube containing the mixture was cooled in ice water and evacuated to about 2 c.m. pressure, sealed and heated for about 6 hours at 60°. The acetonitrile solution was diluted with dry ether (200-300 c.c.) when the solution became turbid. The suspension was kept in cold storage (5° C) overnight. An oily liquid separated at the bottom. The ether was siphoned off and the last traces of ether removed by evaporation *in vacuo*. The oily liquid crystallised in felted needles or platelets on cooling in ice and salt and scratching the liquid. The crystals could not be separated as on pressing them they melted. They were also highly hygroscopic. On allowing the crystals to warm up and melt between 40-50° to remove absorbed solvent (at reduced pressure) they underwent partial decomposition as shown by the formation of solid matter insoluble in acetonitrile. The substance appeared to be tetra-allyl arsonium bromide with acetonitrile of crystallisation. It was highly soluble in water, alcohol, acetonitrile etc., and contains ionic bromine.

Tetra-allyl arsonium bromide mercuribromide was prepared by adding an alcoholic solution of mercuric bromide to an alcoholic solution of tetra-allyl arsonium bromide. A white coarsely crystalline substance separated immediately. The solution was cooled, the crystals filtered and washed with alcohol, m.p. 66°. It crystallised from acetone in small plates. It is highly soluble in acetone and sparingly in alcohol.

The bromine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method. For the mercury estimation the substance was warmed with 1-2 c.c. concentrated nitric acid; the solution diluted and filtered and hydrogen sulphide passed to saturation. To the orange coloured mixture of precipitates about 10 c.c. of yellow ammonium sulphide were added and the mercuric sulphide washed with sodium sulphite to remove traces of sulphur and dried at 105-110° to constant weight. [Found: Br, 35.99; Hg, 29.17. $(C_3H_5)_4AsBr.HgBr_2$ requires Br, 36.29; Hg, 29.52 per cent].

Tetra-allyl arsonium picrate was prepared by adding a saturated aqueous solution of sodium picrate to an alcoholic solution of tetra-allyl arsonium bromide. A yellow precipitate was obtained which gradually became crystalline on adding a few drops of alcohol and cooling. The crystals were washed with ice-cold water, and dried over calcium chloride *in vacuo*, m.p. 82.5°. It is soluble in alcohol but sparingly soluble in ice-cold water. A weighed amount of the substance was heated with 5 c.c. of fuming nitric acid in a Carius tube and the arsenic acid so obtained precipitated as $MgNH_4AsO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Dick, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1934, 93, 429) by adding magnesia mixture, and excess of ammonia to strong alkaline reaction and allowing to stand in a refrigerator overnight. [Found: As, 15.82. $(C_3H_5)_4AsO(NO_3)_2 \cdot C_6H_5$ requires As, 16.05 per cent].

Tetra-allyl Arsonium Hydroxide.—To a concentrated aqueous solution of tetra-allyl arsonium bromide moist silver oxide was added little by little. The brown colour of the oxide changed to yellow gradually. A small excess of silver oxide was added and the mixture agitated, allowed to stand for some time and filtered. The solution was alkaline and probably contained tetra-allyl arsonium hydroxide. On evaporating over sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator, a syrupy liquid was obtained.

The aqueous solution precipitated copper and silver hydroxides from their respective salts, but did not liberate ammonia from ammonium salts. To the above concentrated solution of the base a saturated aqueous solution of picric acid was added. A crystalline yellow solid separated, m.p. 82.5° (mixed m.p. with tetra-allyl arsonium picrate).

Allyl Cacodyl.—The appreciably large amount of residue in B, obtained after distilling off the triallyl arsine was examined. The glass wool which was put in the distilling liquid to prevent bumping fumed in air and burned forming fumes of arsenious oxide. On being dropped into a jar of oxygen it exploded violently producing black particles of carbon and arsenious oxide. That the residual liquid was probably allyl cacodyl was shown as follows.

The glass wool wet with the residue, after distilling off the triallyl arsine completely, was quickly washed with ether and to the ethereal extract a few g. of allyl bromide added and the solution heated to about 60-70°. A syrupy liquid was obtained. A portion of it was dissolved in alcohol and a concentrated aqueous solution of sodium picrate was added. The crystalline substance obtained melted at 82.5° (m.p. of tetra-allyl arsonium picrate).

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